

Analyst Administrator
Date Wednesday, July 6, 2022 4:42 PM

Sample Name	Description	Quality Checks
CAS-133-5_1	Sample 006 By Administrator Date Wednesday, July 06 2022	The Quality Checks give rise to a Weak Bands warning for the sample.